

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECT OF THICKNESS AND MOISTURE CONTENT OF LAMINATED BAMBOO STRIPS ON THERMOFORMING TEMPERATURE

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ABSTRACT

As a renewable material, bamboo is explored to make anchor bolts. In this work, the thermoforming characteristic is utilized to produce U-shaped bamboo anchors. Thermoforming test studies were carried out to investigate the effects of thicknesses and moisture contents. Then, four-point bending tests were conducted to study the flexural properties. It was indicated that the flexural modulus of specimens except for 6.4mm increased and then decreased with increased temperatures. The carbonization degree was related to both temperature and heating time. The initial thermoforming temperature increased with the decreasing moisture content and increasing thickness. Overall, the optimal thermoforming temperature is 210°C for 4.5mm in thickness.

KEYWORDS

laminated bamboo strip; thermoforming temperature; thermal bending; thickness; moisture content

INTRODUCTION

China is a major source of bamboo, known as the 'Kingdom of Bamboo' (Zhou et al. 2018)(Zhou et al. 1974)(Ma et al. 2021). Bamboo is an environment-friendly, natural and renewable material(Bhavna et al. 2015), with the advantages of light weight, high strength, good elasticity, stable performance, low density, higher specific strength, and specific stiffness than wood and ordinary steel (Xian et al. 2015)(Wang, 1996). The development of bamboo in modern construction has been driven by these advantages. With two-thirds of the country's land area, China is a mountainous country (Li, 2017). Exposed mountainous areas are highly susceptible to erosion and soil erosion in the absence of vegetation protection. Anchor bolts are an effective solution to the erosion problem, featuring a small footprint, simple construction,

and high safety (Chen, 2022). Existing anchor rods are mostly made of steel (Kang, 2022), which is costly and has a negative impact on the ecology due to its high carbon emissions (Zhou, 2016). Copper sulfate has the best effect on bamboo to prevent mildew, especially in a humid environment (Wu, 2022). Bamboo, however, is a good ecological alternative to steel for anchors due to its excellent mechanical properties and low cost of distribution. Bamboo lacks radial fibers and is vulnerable to splitting. Using the thermal bending properties of bamboo to make a U-head anchor can make full use of the mechanical properties of the bamboo fiber and reduce the impact of possible splitting. (Li et al. 2021) proposed a bamboo fiber-reinforced polymer tendon with U-head (BFRP tendon) and found that the tension capacity of the BFRP tendon was reliable and the advantages of bamboo fiber could be fully exploited.

However, the physical and mechanical properties of bamboo are changed during the heat treatment. A valuable research direction is to find a reasonable heat treatment method and investigate the factors influencing the mechanical properties of bamboo after the heat treatment. In previous studies, scholars have usually studied the mechanical property changes of bamboo by controlling the temperature and time of thermal bending. Among them, (Bao et al. 2009) studied the effects of temperature and time on the physical and mechanical properties of Moso bamboo, and the results showed that both shrinkage and swelling rates and mechanical properties gradually decreased with increasing temperatures. (Zhang, 2009, 2010) obtained the conclusion from heat-treated Moso bamboo that time and temperature of the heat treatment affected the flexural strength and elastic modulus of bamboo timber to different degrees, among which the effect of time became greater as the heat treatment temperature increased. (Zhou et al. 2019) studied the properties of laminated bamboo under different hygrothermal conditions and found that under high-temperature hydrothermal conditions, the interface of laminated bamboo failed with the collapse of the structure, and the elastic modulus decreased linearly with increasing temperature.

Additionally, there is a significant difference between studies on the thermal bending process, which leads to different conclusions. (Wu et al. 2016) investigated the Moso bamboo heated by high-temperature steam. It was found that after the temperature treatment, the bamboo was able to soften and flatten, and the modulus of elasticity and flexural strength of Moso bamboo tended to decrease as the temperature and time increased. (Hao et al. 2021) investigated the effect of high-temperature treatment of Moso bamboo with methyl silicone oil on the properties of bamboo at different temperatures (140°C-200°C) and times (2h-6h). The results showed that the compressive strength of bamboo parallel to the fiber reached its maximum at 160°C oil heat treatment for 2h, and both compressive strength and modulus of elasticity increased first and then decreased with increasing temperature. (Guan, 2006) used a high and low temperature alternating temperature humidity test chamber to investigate the effect of different humid and hot conditions on the flexural properties of bamboo-wood composite, and the results showed that the flexural modulus of elasticity decreased and then increased with increasing temperature. (Wang et al. 2021) discovered that under the conditions of inert gas (nitrogen), hot oil, and hot water as heat treatment media, 150°C to 250°C and 2 to 6 hours, the moisture content of the bamboo was completely evaporated, the fiber bundles were completely separated and the mechanical properties decreased with the increase of heat treatment time.

In conclusion, bamboo is capable of softening and flattening after high-temperature treatment, and its flexural strength and modulus of elasticity show different trends under different heat treatment conditions, but there are few pieces of research on the thermal bending of laminated bamboo and the factors affecting the thermoforming temperature. Therefore, this paper proposes to make a bamboo anchor with a U-shaped head using the thermal bending properties of laminated bamboo. A heater with a thermostat was used to unilaterally heat fixed-size laminated bamboo strips of different thicknesses and different moisture contents, and their thermoforming temperatures were recorded to find the optimum temperature range for different thicknesses of bamboo strips, at which temperature bamboo strips are selected for four-point bending tests to investigate the effect of treatment temperature on the bending properties of laminated bamboo strips of different thicknesses. The test results can provide experience for the engineering application of bamboo anchors, and also for the application of bamboo structures in construction.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMS

Specimen details

Four thicknesses of laminated bamboo strips were prepared by using laminated bamboo strips made from Moso bamboo in Taojiang County, Yiyang City, Hunan Province, China. To make the experiment more convenient, the strips were cut by a cutting machine and were all made into strips, which have a length and width of 500mm and 21.5mm. During the thermal bending process, 87 specimens were processed three times at each temperature. The details of the specimens are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Specimen number of thermal bending test and four-point bending test

Bamboo thickness (mm)	4.5		5.4		6.4		7.4	
Tot bending temperature (°C)	150		180		230		240	230
	160	180	190	200	240	270	240	230
	170	210	210	230	240	280	250	260
	270	240	220	260	250		270	290
	300		290		260			
	330							
Number of thermal bending test	6*3	3*3	5*3	3*3	4*3	2*3	3*3	3*3
Number of four-point bending test	-	3*6	-	3*6	-	2*6	-	3*6

Note: The number before the multiplication sign indicates the number of groups and the number after the multiplication sign indicates the number of specimens.

Specimens processing and tests process

As shown in Figure 1. The thermal bending process utilized a round heater and a thermostat. The temperature of the bamboo strip was controlled by adjusting the temperature of the thermostat so that the strip was heated to bent to a point where two sides of strips were parallel. The thermostat power was 3000W and the radius of curvature of the round heater was 5cm. The thermal bending test was carried out with a temperature gradient of 10°C to obtain the thermoforming temperature of the bamboo strips. Afterward, the thermal bending process was carried out with a temperature gradient of 30°C. The heating time and the degree of carbonization of the bamboo strips were recorded.

Figure 1: Processes of specimens

The specimens for the four-point bending test were prepared by measuring the inner surface temperature of the bamboo strips with a temperature gun using a plate heater and a thermostat. In the four-point bending test, the heated part of the bamboo strip was subjected to pure bending. The monotonic loading was conducted through a WDW-100E testing machine, all at a loading rate of 8mm/min. The loading was stopped when the mid-span was approximately 2cm from the bottom of the support, and six times were conducted at each temperature. The processes of specimens are shown in Figure 1.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The thermoforming temperature at different thicknesses

The thermoforming temperatures of laminated bamboo strips at different thicknesses are shown in Figure 2. Overall, the thermoforming temperature of the specimens increased as the thickness of specimens increased. Among them, the temperature of the 4.5 mm specimens was 180°C, 200°C for the 5.4 mm ones, 230°C for the 7.4 mm ones, but up to 270°C for the 6.4 mm ones. According to the density of specimens which is shown in Table 2, the density of specimens in the thickness of 6.4mm was higher than the other three thick ones. Therefore, it is assumed that it was the density that caused the temperature anomaly, which resulted in a higher temperature than the 7.4mm specimens.

Figure 2: Temperature setting and the relationship between thickness and thermoforming temperature

Thermal bending effect of specimens of the same thickness at different temperatures

The thermal bending of the specimens is shown in Table 2. In the results of the 4.5 mm thick bamboo strip, when the temperature of the thermostat was increased to 240°C, the average heating time of the specimens was the shortest. This may be due to the fact that there are no bamboo joints in the heated parts of the specimens in this group, so the fibers softened more easily when heated. It could also be because bamboo strips were thin and carbonized severely when the temperature rose, resulting in a carbonized layer on their surfaces which caused the heating time to increase. When the thickness of specimens is 5.4mm, the average temperature on the inner surface of the bamboo strip was the same when the thermostat was set to 200°C and 230°C, because the heating bending time was significantly shorter when the temperature was increased and the heating rate of the bamboo strip was increased. In addition, the results of the 6.4 mm specimens appeared abnormal. When the thermostat temperature was increased to 270°C, the bamboo strips started to bent and their inner surfaces were almost completely carbonized. When the temperature of the thermostat increased, the heating time increased and the average temperature of the inner surface was about the same as before. It is due to the higher average density, lower average moisture content, and higher flexural modulus of the 280°C-treated specimens, which made them have better flexural capacity. In summary, under the same thickness, as the temperature of the thermostat increases, the thermoforming temperature of the inner surface of the specimens increases, and the required heating time is gradually reduced. Additionally, when the temperature is above a certain value, its average heating time tends to change slowly.

Table 2: Specimens heating time at different temperature

Bamboo thickness (mm)	Temperature of thermostat (°C)	Average temperature of inner bamboo (°C)	Average heating time (s)	Average density (g/cm ³)	Average moisture content (%)
4.5	180	188	520	0.76	7.76
	210	198	492	0.92	7.86
	240	220	246	0.73	7.77

	270	251	326	0.79	7.96
	300	245	280	0.76	7.80
	330	282	263	0.89	7.24
5.4	200	198	592	1.61	7.79
	230	198	224	1.43	7.48
	260	220	220	1.48	7.47
6.4	270	241	308	1.57	7.64
	280	238	333	1.81	7.55
7.4	230	218	802	0.71	7.79
	260	226	360	0.63	7.51
	290	256	328	0.78	7.46

During the thermal bending process of four thicknesses of bamboo strips, when the temperature of the thermostat was above a certain value, white smoke and a pungent smell were produced, which contributed to the environmental pollution. Meanwhile, the inner surface of specimens where it meets the round heater was carbonized. When the temperature increased, the carbonization became greater. Eventually, a black carbonized layer was formed in the heated section, which affected the appearance, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Carbonization of the inner surface of specimens

Therefore, considering that the heating time should not be too long and the carbonization degree should not be too high, the most optimal temperature range for thermal bending at four thicknesses was finally obtained, and the four-point bending tests were prepared based on this temperature range.

Four-point bending tests

The load-displacement curves for all specimens are shown in Figure 4. The load-displacement curves fluctuate considerably due to the small thickness of the specimens and the development of internal cracks during the loading process. Comparing the test curves of the four thicknesses, each specimen went through the elastic and plastic stages respectively, and the fluctuation of the curve in the plastic stage increased as the thickness increased. In the elastic stage, the stiffness of the specimens remained constant. The load-displacement curves entered the elastic-plastic stage when the upper bamboo fibers were compressed and yielded in the pure bending section. When the curve reached its peak, the test stopped as the deflection of the specimen

reached the demand for test stop or crack occurred.

Figure 4: Load-displacement relationships of different thicknesses at different temperatures.

The damage pattern of four-point bending specimens is shown in Figure 5. Because the specimen is too thin, most of the specimens did not experience significant damage behavior when the test was stopped at approximately 2cm from the bottom of the support in the mid-span, as shown in Figure 5(a). Among the 6.4mm, and 7.4mm specimens, five specimens showed the damage pattern as shown in Figure 5(b). The fiber at the bottom of the specimen

fractured below the loading actuator, followed by the rapid development of cracks along the fiber direction until a complete loss of bearing capacity. For both failure modes, no significant damage was initially observed on the specimens. When the thickness was larger than 4.5 mm, a slight sound of cracked fibers could be heard during the loading process, which became apparent as the thickness increased.

$$E = \frac{23Fl^3}{108xbt^3} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$E = \frac{Fl}{\epsilon bt^2} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where E represents flexural modulus (GPa); F represent the load (N); x represents the displacement (mm); l represents the length of the specimen (mm); b represents the width of the specimen (mm); t represents the thickness of the specimen (mm); ϵ represents the strain.

Figure 5: Typical failure modes

According to equation (1) (2), the flexural modulus of the specimens was calculated, and the results are shown in Table 3. According to equation (1), the flexural modulus of the specimens of different thicknesses was calculated after different temperature treatments. As shown in Figure 5, the flexural modulus of specimens treated with one side heated did not increase. Moreover, under different thicknesses, the flexural modulus increased and then decreased with increasing temperature, and there was a suitable temperature at which the flexural modulus was maximized.

Table 3: The flexural modulus of specimens at different temperatures

Bamboo thickness (mm)	Temperature of thermostat (°C)	Flexural modulus of the unheated surface (GPa)	Flexural modulus of the heated surface (GPa)	Flexural modulus (GPa)
4.5	180	6.81(10.38)	9.41(11.47)	8.97(22.46)
	210	13.93(14.05)	10.37(11.41)	12.38(13.60)
	240	11.08(13.42)	9.36(21.04)	9.27(12.37)
5.4	200	7.32(33.74)	7.76(23.95)	7.69(23.58)
	230	9.88(42.43)	8.60(33.70)	8.62(35.97)
	260	7.33(34.53)	6.51(19.41)	7.23(25.89)
6.4	270	11.75(14.78)	9.07(22.41)	11.06(8.49)

	280	12.77(29.02)	9.77(10.85)	11.68(11.54)
7.4	230	9.54(29.36)	8.47(21.61)	9.76(13.34)
	260	10.36(27.97)	8.41(17.69)	10.64(7.69)
	290	7.63(22.02)	9.87(37.54)	9.19(7.10)

Note: The value in parentheses indicates the coefficient of variation (%).

Figure 5: The flexural modulus of specimens at different thicknesses

Furthermore, the flexural modulus of the heated and unheated surfaces of the specimens was calculated according to equation (2) and the results showed that the flexural modulus of the heated inner surface of the specimens was lower than that of the unheated outer surface, except for the two groups of 4.5 mm specimens treated at 180°C and 5.4 mm specimens treated at 200°C. This is probably because the flexural modulus decreased due to the softening of the fibers after they have been heated and returned to room temperature.

In summary, the flexural modulus of the specimens is related to the temperature they are bent, and there is an optimum temperature at which different thicknesses of specimens achieve optimum flexural modulus, above or below which the flexural modulus decreases. There is no clear relationship between the flexural modulus and the thickness.

The influence of moisture contents

$$T_2 = \frac{L}{\lambda S} P + T_1 \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

During the thermal bending process, the thermoforming temperature of the specimen with a thickness of 6.4 mm was too high and the data for the heating time appeared abnormal. To obtain the theoretical thermoforming temperature of the bamboo strips under normal conditions, it was assumed that the power of the heat source was 25W (taking heat dissipation into account) and the thermal conductivity of the bamboo material was 1.0-1.4 kJ/m·h·°C (Wu et al. 2021). Using a very thin bamboo strip for thermal bending, the thermoforming temperature was 82°C, assuming the same temperature on the inside and outside surface of the bamboo strip. Since the essence of thermal bending is that the fibers are softened by heating, and whether the bamboo strip could be bent to 180°C depends on the fibers on the outside surface, we take 82°C as the

thermoforming temperature of the outside surface of the bamboo strip. By using the relationship between the thermal resistance and thermal conductivity, the inner temperatures of bamboo strips of different thicknesses when bending were introduced according to equation (3), as shown in Table 4. It was indicated that when the thickness of the bamboo strip was 6.4mm, the thermoforming temperature of the inner surface should be between 203.89°C and 252.64°C. For all other thicknesses, thermoforming temperatures were within the temperature range obtained from the calculations. Therefore, all specimens undergoing the thermal bending were tested for moisture content, placed in an oven at 105°C, and weighed every two hours until the difference in mass between the two weightings did not exceed five percent of the total mass. The results showed that the average moisture content of the 6.4mm thick bamboo strip specimens was 7.35%, while the average moisture contents of the remaining thicknesses were 7.68%, 7.64%, and 7.68% respectively. Therefore, the difference in moisture content was the reason why the high thermoforming temperature of the specimens with a thickness of 6.4mm during the thermal bending process, as shown in Figure 2.

Table 4: Theoretical and experimental thermoforming temperature of specimens

Bamboo thickness (mm)	Average density (g/cm ³)	Average moisture content (%)	Theoretical thermoforming temperature (°C)	Experimental thermoforming temperature (°C)
4.5	0.78	7.68	168~202	180
5.4	0.66	7.64	185~226	200
6.4	0.65	7.35	204~253	270
7.4	0.75	7.68	223~279	230

To verify the effect of moisture content on the thermoforming temperature, 4.5mm thick bamboo strips were taken, cut into 400mm long strips, and bent after treating for 0.5h, 1h, 1.5h, and 2h in the oven respectively. As shown in Table 5, there was a close relationship between the moisture content and the thermoforming temperature. As the average moisture content decreases, the thermoforming temperature rises. Therefore, during the previous thermal bending process, the thermoforming temperature was significantly higher for bamboo strips 6.4mm thick than for other thicknesses.

where T_1 is the temperature on the surface away from the heat source (°C), T_2 is the temperature on the surface close to the heat source (°C), P is the power of the heat source (W), λ is the thermal conductivity and S is the heat transfer area.

Table 5: Specimens temperature at different moisture contents

Drying time (h)	Average moisture content (%)	Temperature of thermostat (°C)	Temperature of the inner surface (°C)
0.5	3.37%	200	195.07
1	2.69%	220	213.33
1.5	1.69%	240	228.00
2	0.93%	260	239.00

CONCLUSIONS

This paper conducted a thermal bending process and four-point bending tests using laminated bamboo strips of different thicknesses to investigate the thermoforming temperature, with the aim of exploring the effect of thickness and moisture content on the thermoforming performance. The conclusions can be drawn as follows:

- (1) The thermoforming temperature of the specimens increased as the thickness of the specimens increased or the moisture content decreased,
- (2) With the increase of the thermal bending temperature, the time required for the thermoforming temperature of the specimen decreased, but the carbonization of the surface increased, and the carbonized layer on the surface of the bamboo might influence the time required for its thermal bending.
- (3) The flexural modulus of the bamboo strip was related to the temperature during the thermal bending. Each thickness of bamboo was suggested an optimal temperature that allowed it to obtain the best flexural modulus.
- (4) In the production of U-shaped bamboo anchors, the use of 4.5mm bamboo strips with the thermoforming temperature of 210°C was recommended due to its economical production and excellent mechanical strength.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.